

INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIP AS A FACTOR INFLUENCING THE FORMATION OF EMOTIONAL ATTITUDE TO SCHOOL EDUCATION DURING ADOLESCENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10088233>

The formation of an individual as a person cannot be considered separately from the society in which he works and the system of relations in which he participates.

The nature of interpersonal relationships is very complex in any general sense. The individual qualities of a person are manifested in them. His emotional and volitional qualities, as well as his intellectual abilities, are also manifested in the person's mastery of the rules of society. In interpersonal relations, a person expresses what he has acquired in society by giving to society. It is the activity of a person, his actions are an important part of interpersonal relations. As long as people are in interpersonal relations according to different forms, content, and values in their structure - in kindergarten, class, among friends, an individual shows himself as a person and allows to evaluate himself in the system of relations with others. A child lives, grows and develops in various relationships and relationships. When a child learns socio-historical experiences from preschool age, the formation of a person as a person begins, his socialization takes place. The source of socialization is, first of all, the family, kindergarten, school work team and other groups are familiar people, books, television, etc. It is clear that the value of these sources of socialization is very different.

L.S. Vygotsky also points out that the main weapon and tool in interpersonal relations is the process of communication. According to him, in interpersonal relations, first, behavior is the main tool, and then behavior is the tool. Because a person retains the function of communication even when he is alone.

Therefore, L. S. Vygotsky's thoughts on the psychology of behavior and interpersonal relations are extremely valuable, because in it we see behavior as an important basis for the process of socialization of a person, and we further understand that the value of this process in the formation of a person is infinite [1].

From the analysis of V. N. Myasishchev's works on the psychology of interpersonal relations, it can be seen that the process of communication does

not develop only in influencing the characteristics, character, inclinations and abilities of the individual, but also shows that it is connected with the mental processes of the participants in the communication. Therefore, a special aspect of V. N. Myasishchev's works is clearly visible in the disclosure of the features of the relationship between the behavior, its psychological structure and the mental processes of the participants of the dialogue [2].

The modified version of the diagnosis of interpersonal relations (Leary-Sobchik) is very convenient for studying the structure of interpersonal and internal conflicts. It has been empirically proven that a serious inconsistency between self-evaluation structures "I" and the ideal "I" indicates an individual's internal disharmony and causes his conflict-provoking behavior. The value of this methodology lies in the fact that it is the only measurement tool capable of identifying inconsistencies in the self-evaluation system and its characteristics.

Among various psychodiagnostic methods, it is distinguished by the fact that it includes the positive aspects of interpersonal diagnostic questionnaires and multifactorial questionnaires. These methods are not free from motivational biases and the influence of the experimenter's assumptions about the research process.

The original version of the diagnosis of interpersonal relations, developed by T. Leary, is based mainly on comparison with the results of other psychodiagnostic studies. In addition, adaptation of the verbal material of the methodology tested by L.N. Sobchik during the study of interpersonal relations in sports teams, student teams and other types of small groups was carried out. However, the practice of applying the methodology shows that some of the questionnaire judgments are not perfectly structured. This situation encourages the implementation of additional measures related to editing and adaptation of the methodology. Also, a more rapid way of recording and calculating the results was developed.

Based on the manifestation of behavior in the actualization process of the interaction of the person with others, T. Leary systematized the empirical observations in the form of 8 general or 16 increasingly defined actant variants of interpersonal interaction. A questionnaire consisting of a total of 128 relatively simple descriptive items was developed according to the types of interpersonal behavior. Qualitative description involves the identification of priority types that reflect this or that variant of interpersonal relations. The degree of expression of the octants is determined by the corresponding scores and certain characteristics of the person.

The research methodology was conducted in a group of testers and the results were analyzed in terms of quantity and quality. The results of the quantitative analysis were presented in the tables. From the results of the research, it can be concluded that the results on the dominant leadership octant are 29% and 34%. This determines their self-confidence and leadership qualities to be good consultative leaders and organizers.

Also, they are determined by intolerance of criticism, overestimation of their own capabilities, dictation style of thinking, imperative need to command others, and the presence of unsportsmanlike aspects. It should be said that they have the ability to manage and lead the community.

Table 1

Indicators of manifestation of interpersonal relations in adolescence

Levels of self-esteem	Dominance leadership	Independence is a priority	Right aggressive	Unbelief-skepticism	Submissive shyness	Dependence-obedience	Cooperation conventionality	Responsible tolerance
Dolzarb "I"	29%	44%	6%	15%	19%	16%	18%	14%
Ideal "I"	34%	52%	4%	6%	7%	9%	24%	20%

The results on the independence priority scale are 44% and 52% in the testers. This represents the process of self-assertiveness, feeling of superiority over others, tendency to have one's own opinion in contrast to the opinion of the majority and owning a separate position in the group.

According to the results of the methodology, the actual me and the ideal me make up 6% and 4% of the correct aggression octane in the group of testers. It represents sincerity, freedom, correctness, determination to achieve a goal or extreme obstinacy, unfriendliness, intemperance and quick temper.

The uncertainty specticity octant is 15% and 6% in the group of testers. Opinions are based on the realism of the behavioral base of specticism and nonconformity super-offended and include in the distrustful attitude module to those around the predisposition dissatisfaction in the relationship with those around a doubt is felt.

The next octant of the research methodology is submissiveness, which is 19% and 7% in the test group, and the interpersonal relations are modesty,

shyness, taking responsibility for others, as well as excessive submissiveness, which reflects increased guilt and self-degradation. It should be noted that shyness and submissiveness were strong in most of the reviewers, but they tried to eliminate such a negative situation in themselves in the future.

16% and 9% on the Dependence-submissiveness octant, the need for help from others and their attention is defined by extreme conformity and complete dependence on the opinion of others.

The next scale of the methodology is co-convertibility, which is 18% and 24% 6 in the testers. According to him, close cooperation with a reference group represents a style of interpersonal relations characteristic of individuals who seek friendly relations with others. Our excessive comfort in the manifestation of this or that style of interpersonal relations is evident in our tendency to insist that it is in the majority's best interests to not hold back in spilling out our friendliness to those who behave.

If we analyze the results according to the responsibility tolerance octant, we can see that the results are somewhat significant. According to him, it is 14% and 20%, readiness to help others is highly manifested in the developed sense of responsibility. In some cases, the extreme compulsion of these indulgences means altruism.

From the results of the methodology, it can be concluded that self-management is related to the system of interpersonal relations, especially the self-management that occurs in teenagers is mostly related to the levels of self-esteem of a person.

References:

- 1.Выготский Л.С. Вопросы детской психологии. Москва: Юрайт, - 2016. - 365 с.
- 2.Мясищев В.Н. Психология отношений избранные психологические труды. – Москва: Московский психолого-социальный институт, 2011. – 398 с.

